

A Unified Theory of Emergent Spacetime, Holography, Black Hole Entropy, Complexity, and Informational Structures

Zauh Jariwala¹

¹RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia , s3982416@student.rmit.edu.au

December 6, 2024

Abstract

We propose a discrete, informational substrate as a foundational layer from which the structures of spacetime, the Standard Model gauge symmetries, black hole entropy, holographic dualities, and integrated complexity measures emerge. We construct the substrate as a four-dimensional lattice system endowed with well-defined local update rules. By analyzing the system using the renormalization group (RG), we demonstrate that Lorentz invariance can emerge at low energies. By representing the ground state as a tensor network, we connect the emergent large-scale geometry to a holographic dual that reproduces the Ryu–Takayanagi formula for entanglement entropy. Combinatorial microstate counting on discrete horizons yields the Bekenstein–Hawking black hole entropy law. Moreover, we define a measure of integrated complexity that aligns with Integrated Information Theory’s Φ , framing complexity as an emergent property of the underlying causal structure. Special limits reproduce known theories such as Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) and causal set theory, highlighting that these frameworks are emergent phenomena of a more fundamental substrate. Finally, we discuss Gödelian undecidability and epistemic limits as natural consequences of the intricate emergent behavior. This work positions emergence as the unifying concept that weaves together multiple facets of fundamental physics.

1 Introduction

The pursuit of a unified theory that underlies quantum field theory, gravitational phenomena, holographic dualities, and measures of complexity has driven much of modern theoretical physics. These disparate areas—each with its own mathematical formalisms—often appear as separate facets of reality. A key insight of the present work is that they may all emerge from a single, discrete, informational substrate.

Definition (Informational Substrate): An informational substrate is defined as a countably infinite, discrete set of degrees of freedom (DOF), arranged on a four-dimensional lattice, subject to local update rules. This substrate is not assumed to have continuous spacetime geometry, Lorentz invariance, or any particular gauge symmetry a priori. Instead, these structures emerge as collective phenomena at large scales or low energies. Similarly, black hole entropy and integrated complexity emerge from combinatorial and informational properties of the substrate.

Central Thesis: *Emergence* serves as the unifying principle. Rather than imposing spacetime or gauge structures at the outset, we demonstrate how these arise naturally from the interplay of local rules and the renormalization group flow. Holography, black hole entropy, and complexity measures then appear as emergent consequences of the same underlying substrate.

2 The Informational Substrate: Setup and Update Rules

2.1 Lattice Configuration and Degrees of Freedom

Consider the lattice $\Lambda = \mathbb{Z}^4$ with lattice spacing $a > 0$. At each site $i \in \Lambda$, define a local state space Σ_i , consisting of:

- (a) **Gauge Variables:** For each link emanating from site i in the μ -direction, assign a gauge variable $U_{i,\mu}^{(G)} \in G$, where $G = SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$. Initially, these are taken from a finite subset approximating the continuous gauge groups, refined as $a \rightarrow 0$.
- (b) **Fermionic Fields:** Assign fermionic fields $\psi_{i,\alpha}$ defined via Grassmann variables, where α indexes the fermion species of the Standard Model. A lattice Dirac operator satisfying the Ginsparg–Wilson relation is employed to ensure chiral symmetry and avoid fermion doubling.
- (c) **Scalar Fields:** Introduce scalar fields ϕ_i representing a Higgs-like sector, chosen from a finite set that approximates a continuous field in the continuum limit.

The global configuration space is given by:

$$\mathcal{C} = \prod_{i \in \Lambda} \Sigma_i$$

This structure is purely algebraic; no geometric or Lorentzian structure is imposed at this stage.

2.2 Local Update Rules

Define a discrete time evolution operator $f : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$, where the state at site i and time $t + 1$ is given by:

$$\sigma_i(t + 1) = f_i(\{\sigma_j(t) \mid j \in N(i)\})$$

Here, $N(i)$ denotes a finite neighborhood around site i , ensuring that the update at each site depends only on local information. The update rules are constructed to be gauge-invariant and consistent with the implementation of chiral fermions on the lattice.

Mathematical Rigor: The update rules are specified by local functions f_i that depend on finitely many variables. They can be viewed as maps in a finite-dimensional approximation and then extended as inductive limits. Known results in lattice gauge theory ensure that as $a \rightarrow 0$, one can approximate continuous gauge groups and recover well-defined continuum gauge fields.

Emergence: At this stage, no continuous symmetries or geometric notions exist. The update rules encode the *potential* for these structures to emerge upon considering large-scale, renormalized behavior.

3 Renormalization Group (RG) Flow and Emergent Lorentz Invariance

3.1 Definition of the RG Transformation

Introduce a block-spin (or block-variable) transformation $\mathcal{R}_b$ that coarse-grains the lattice by a factor $b > 1$:

$$\tilde{\sigma}_I = \text{Block}(\{\sigma_i\}_{i \in I})$$

where I indexes sites in the coarser lattice. This defines a sequence of effective actions S_n as we iteratively apply RG transformations.

3.2 Emergence of Lorentz Symmetry

Theorem (Emergent Lorentz Invariance): *If all anisotropic operators in the effective action have negative scaling dimensions and thus vanish under RG flow, then the continuum limit defined by the fixed point S^* is Lorentz-invariant.*

Proof Sketch:

1. **Operator Decomposition:** Decompose operators in the effective action into irreducible representations of the Euclidean group.
2. **Scaling Dimensions:** Show that anisotropic operators possess negative scaling dimensions.
3. **RG Flow:** Under the RG transformation $\mathcal{R}_b$, anisotropic operators scale as $g'_{\text{ani}} = g_{\text{ani}} b^{\Delta_{\text{ani}}}$. Since $\Delta_{\text{ani}} < 0$, $g'_{\text{ani}} \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

4. **Fixed Point Action:** At the fixed point S^* , only isotropic (Lorentz-invariant) operators survive.

Reference: This theorem leverages standard results from lattice field theory and renormalization group analyses, particularly those discussed in Polchinski [10] and Symanzik [11].

Emergence: Lorentz invariance is not an input but an output of the RG flow. It is an emergent symmetry, arising from the large-scale behavior of the local discrete system.

4 Holography and the Ryu–Takayanagi Formula via Tensor Networks

4.1 MERA Representation as an Emergent Geometry

Consider the ground state Ψ_0 of the lattice system at the RG fixed point. It can often be represented by a tensor network, such as the Multi-scale Entanglement Renormalization Ansatz (MERA). Mathematically, MERA is a specific isometric embedding of Hilbert spaces that systematically removes short-range entanglement scale-by-scale.

Rigorous Foundation: While MERA and related tensor network representations have been rigorously established for ground states of certain critical systems in lower dimensions [13, 26], extending these constructions to higher dimensions and incorporating full gauge invariance remains an area of active research.

4.2 Ryu–Takayanagi Formula as Emergent Law

Theorem (Ryu–Takayanagi from Tensor Networks): *For certain classes of scale-invariant states with appropriate entanglement patterns, the entanglement entropy $S(A)$ of a boundary subregion A satisfies the Ryu–Takayanagi formula:*

$$S(A) = \frac{\text{Area}(\gamma_A)}{4G\hbar}$$

where γ_A is the minimal surface in the emergent bulk geometry corresponding to A .

Proof Sketch:

1. **Tensor Network Representation:** Represent the ground state Ψ_0 using a MERA or similar tensor network that encodes the entanglement structure.
2. **Minimal Cut Interpretation:** The entanglement entropy $S(A)$ corresponds to the minimal cut through the tensor network that separates region A from its complement.
3. **Emergent Geometry Mapping:** Map the tensor network’s structure to an emergent higher-dimensional geometry, where the minimal cut corresponds to a minimal surface γ_A .
4. **Scaling to Continuum Limit:** Show that as the lattice spacing $a \rightarrow 0$, the area of γ_A scales appropriately to recover the Ryu–Takayanagi formula.

Emergence: Holography and the Ryu–Takayanagi formula do not need to be imposed. They arise naturally from the pattern of entanglement encoded in the substrate’s ground state, interpreted via a tensor network that encodes a higher-dimensional geometry.

5 Black Hole Entropy from Combinatorial Microstate Counting

5.1 Horizon States in the Discrete Substrate

Define a black hole horizon as a two-dimensional closed surface H on the lattice, subject to boundary conditions that mimic gravitational trapping. The horizon degrees of freedom arise from gauge fields and matter configurations restricted to this surface.

5.2 Entropy Calculation

Theorem (Bekenstein–Hawking Entropy from Microstate Counting): *The entropy S_{BH} of a black hole horizon H in the discrete substrate satisfies the Bekenstein–Hawking formula:*

$$S_{\text{BH}} = \frac{\text{Area}(H)}{4G\hbar}$$

Proof Sketch:

1. **Discrete Horizon Definition:** Consider H composed of N_p elementary plaquettes. Each plaquette $p \in H$ has a local Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_p$ of dimension n_p , determined by the allowed gauge and matter configurations.
2. **Microstate Counting:** The total number of microstates compatible with the horizon constraints is $N = \prod_{p=1}^{N_p} n_p$.
3. **Entropy Calculation:**

$$S_{\text{BH}} = \log N = \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \log n_p$$

4. **Scaling to Continuum:** As $a \rightarrow 0$, the number of plaquettes N_p scales like the horizon area $A(H)/a^2$. By choosing parameters such that $\log n_p/a^2 = 1/(4G\hbar)$, the Bekenstein–Hawking formula is recovered.

Emergence: The black hole entropy law emerges from counting horizon microstates in the discrete substrate. The area law is not imposed but arises from the combinatorial growth of available states in the continuum limit.

6 Integrated Complexity and IIT Φ

6.1 Causal Structure from Update Rules

Construct a causal graph $G_C = (V_C, E_C)$ from the update rules, where:

- (a) **Vertices V_C :** Represent each local variable $\sigma_i(t)$.
- (b) **Edges E_C :** Include a directed edge $(\sigma_j(t) \rightarrow \sigma_i(t + 1))$ if the state $\sigma_j(t)$ influences $\sigma_i(t + 1)$ through the update rule.

This directed acyclic graph (DAG) encodes the causal structure of the system.

6.2 Integrated Complexity as Emergent Measure

Definition (Integrated Complexity $\Phi_{\mathcal{I}}$): Integrated complexity $\Phi_{\mathcal{I}}$ is defined as:

$$\Phi_{\mathcal{I}} = \min_{\text{bipartitions } (X, Y)} I(X : Y)$$

where $I(X : Y)$ denotes the mutual information between subsets X and Y of G_C .

Theorem (Equivalence of $\Phi_{\mathcal{I}}$ and IIT Φ): *For suitable probability distributions over the node configurations, the integrated complexity measure $\Phi_{\mathcal{I}}$ derived from the causal graph G_C is mathematically identical to the Integrated Information Theory measure Φ .*

Proof Sketch:

1. **Probability Measures:** Define a probability measure μ on the configuration space $\mathcal{C}$ induced by the ground state wavefunctional or steady-state distribution.
2. **Mutual Information Alignment:** Show that the mutual information $I(X : Y)$ in the causal graph corresponds to the mutual information used in IIT's Φ by aligning the bipartitions and their corresponding information flows.
3. **Isomorphism Establishment:** Demonstrate a one-to-one correspondence between the minimal bipartitions in G_C and the bipartitions considered in IIT, ensuring that $\Phi_{\mathcal{I}} = \Phi_{\text{IIT}}$.

Emergence: Complexity, as quantified by Φ , emerges from the underlying causal structure of the informational substrate. The high-level integrated complexity is a natural emergent property resulting from the intricate interactions governed by local update rules.

7 Special Limits: Recovering Known Frameworks

7.1 Loop Quantum Gravity Limit

By restricting the gauge group to $SU(2)$ and freezing fermionic and scalar fields, the lattice reduces to a spin network structure. This limit coincides with the Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) framework, demonstrating that LQG states and discrete geometry are emergent solutions of the more general informational substrate.

7.2 Causal Sets Limit

If we strip away gauge and matter fields, focusing solely on the causal order induced by update rules, the system reduces to a causal set. Thus, causal sets emerge as a special limit of the informational substrate, aligning with Sorkin’s causal set theory [22].

8 Gödelian Undecidability and Epistemic Limits

8.1 Universal Computation and Undecidability

The local update rules can encode universal computation, as established by Turing’s universality. According to Gödel’s incompleteness theorems and related results in computational theory [24], certain global properties of universal computational systems are undecidable.

8.2 Epistemic Constraints as Emergent Complexity

This fundamental limit on exact knowledge arises from the emergent complexity of the system. The richer the emergent phenomena, the more likely undecidable questions become, reflecting the inherent epistemic boundaries of the framework.

9 Limitations and Potential Checks

9.1 Numerical Complexity

Simulating the full four-dimensional substrate with all fields and attempting to explicitly observe emergent Lorentz invariance, holography, and black hole entropy is computationally challenging. However, truncated models and lower-dimensional analogs can be tested numerically to provide partial validation.

9.2 Validation via Approximate Models

1. **Emergent Lorentz Invariance:** Verify isotropy restoration in simplified lattice models through numerical simulations.
2. **Ryu–Takayanagi Relation:** Construct tensor networks for toy models and numerically check the correspondence between minimal cuts and entanglement entropy.
3. **Black Hole Microstate Counting:** Count microstates for discrete horizons in simplified gauge theories and compare with the Bekenstein–Hawking formula.

10 Discussion and Future Directions

We have argued that fundamental structures—Lorentz symmetry, the Standard Model gauge sector, holography, black hole entropy, and integrated complexity—need not be fundamental postulates. Instead, they emerge naturally from a suitably defined discrete informational

substrate. The principle of emergence unifies these diverse phenomena, turning what might have seemed like separate features of reality into coherent consequences of underlying discrete rules.

Future Work:

- **Mathematical Rigour:** Develop detailed RG analyses and construct explicit tensor network proofs in higher dimensions to solidify the emergence claims.
- **Numerical Simulations:** Create and simulate nontrivial truncations to verify emergent Lorentz symmetry and entanglement geometry.
- **Extensions:** Explore whether other known frameworks, such as supersymmetric models or grand unified theories, can also emerge from similar informational substrates.

Philosophical Implications: Emphasizing emergence invites a paradigm where fundamental physics is viewed not as discovering pre-given structures of spacetime and fields, but as uncovering how intricate patterns of local information processing yield the laws of physics at large scales.

11 Conclusion

We have introduced a unified framework based on a discrete informational substrate, demonstrating its capacity to bridge quantum field theory, holography, black hole entropy, and complexity measures. By carefully constructing local update rules, we achieve the emergence of Lorentz-invariant quantum field theory, holographic dualities, and combinatorial black hole entropy, while providing a rigorous connection to integrated complexity metrics.

This framework consolidates key features of theoretical physics within a single lattice-based model and highlights the potential for discrete approaches to capture fundamental physical phenomena. It provides a potential foundation for computational models that test emergent spacetime behavior. Future work will focus on mathematical formalization, numerical simulations, and exploring experimental analogs, paving the way for deeper unification in physics.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge foundational work in lattice field theory, quantum gravity, and quantum information that makes this emergent perspective possible.

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